

Design, Implementation, and Improvement of the Course for Master's Degree Program in Industry 4.0: A Case Study in Digital Factory Subject

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to propose the procedures of design, implementation, and improvement for the specific course developed of project named Curriculum Development of Master's Degree Program in Industrial Engineering for Thailand Sustainable Smart Industry (MSIE 4.0), which is funded by the Erasmus and program of the European Union. The digital factory subject, which is one of 16 courses in MSIE 4.0 provides effective elements: program learning outcomes (PLOs), course learning outcomes (CLOs), assessment methods, course syllabus, and teaching guidelines. Moreover, the steps proposed in this study demonstrate the acquisition of knowledges, skills, and competencies based on the perspectives of stakeholders via its course description. There are five important CLOs: understanding the different between traditional factory and digital manufactory, applying digital manufacturing technologies e.g. cyber physical system, additive manufacturing, virtual reality augmented reality, additive manufacturing, sensor device technologies, and robotics/automated guided vehicle in a manufacturing complex requirement, analyzing works in both information-managed and file-based environments for the development of robotic and automated production systems. and implementing digital inventory to manage incoming and outgoing goods. Furthermore, the well-designed scoring rubrics of each CLO are established to measure students' learning experiences and are used to find the area of improvement at the end of every modules. For the implementation, 12 students register for the subject in the second term of 2019 between June to October at King Mongkut's University of Technology North Bangkok (KMUTNB). The students are observed by many assessment methods after they finished the modules. The students' learning experiences are summarized and improved based on the levels of CLOs. The scrupulous steps of this study can be used to guide instructors for designing other course and related issues. Moreover, the students, who accomplish this course can work in a rapid fusion of technologies for the articulation of stakeholder needs.

Keywords: Digital Factory; Rubric; Course Learning Outcome (CLO); Assessment of Learning.

1 Introduction

A curriculum is a plan for learning (Taba, 1962), it refers to the lessons and contents taught in universities or in specific programs (Vanderlinde, van Braak, & Hermans, 2009). In the past centuries, the curriculum has been designed by teacher with interested educational purposes. However, presently curriculum must be to meet the needs of stakeholders since the teachers' perspectives are inadequate to create an effective curriculum. The design of curriculum is a challenging task because it involves many elements: contents, teaching strategies, learning experiences, assessments, evaluations, and pedagogic requirements necessary. The fundamental goal of curriculum design is to improve student learning, which demonstrates when student completed or participated in a course or program. In a globalizing of technological advancement and economic growth in the era of Industry 4.0 (Sackey & Bester, 2016), the curriculum design has become the difficult task since automation and robotization have been adopted to increase their productivity, especially manufacturing enterprises (Guberman & Leikin, 2013). Therefore, the development of student based on curriculum is a critical task, the design of curriculum can be employed to overcome this problem. The new curriculum must be designed to meet the needs of all stakeholders.

The Curriculum Development of Master's Degree Program in Industrial Engineering for Thailand Sustainable Smart Industry (MSIE 4.0) project funded by the European Commission aims to develop a magister scientiae degree (MSc) for industrial engineering (IE) aligned with needs of Industry 4.0. In order to achieve the goals,

16 modern courses of Master's degree in IE are designed for learning experience and equipped with new teaching and learning materials. These courses are constructed based on structure and academic program learning outcomes (Nitkiewicz, Ayutthaya, Koomsap, Lima, & Chattinnawat, 2019). Then, a course assessment is employed to evaluate a feasibility of the modern curricula at the partner universities. The digital factory subject, which is one of 16 courses has been created to serve many purposes within the smart factory. This course, which has lectured in key subject areas requires an implementing the various digital technologies with minimal human assistance: additive manufacturing, intelligent robotics, industrial internet of things, cyber-physical system, global cloud manufacturing (Kang et al., 2016; Koothongsumrit & Luangpaiboon, 2020). Therefore, the digital factory is discussed.

2 Course Design

Designing an academic course is not easy. It is an intricate process that needs to be carefully thought through and involves much strategic decision-making. To date, the course design can be defined as the step-by-step process used to improve modern and deliberate overall outline, mapping content to learning objectives in the course. This section describes a procedure to design the course outline of the digital factory subject by considering four dimensions of course design: stakeholders, objectives, data, and techniques (Gottipati & Shankaraman, 2017). In this study, there are six phases for designing the digital factory's course outline.

2.1 Program Learning Outcomes Design

Program learning outcomes (PLOs) refer to domain expertise and knowledges that students should be able to articulate after the completion of courses (Hammami, Saeed, Mathkour, & Arafah, 2019). In this study, PLOs of the subject are designed to conform with the Industry 4.0 data, they include selection of content, development of teaching strategies, and teaching materials or resources. Graduates should be able to complete the following PLOs: (1) apply knowledge and methods from the advanced science of industrial engineering to design, model and manage Industry 4.0 related complex industrial systems; (2) implement smart production and co-created product design and development concepts; (3) utilize big data and real time data analytics for supporting smart production, product design, and advanced manufacturing process; (4) exploit online connectivity for strengthening business capability; (5) improve sustainability by applying IE related knowledge and competences; (6) conduct research in the field of IE; (7) manage Industry 4.0 related projects; (8) manage smart production systems and supply chains; (9) lead, manage, work and communicate effectively in interdisciplinary, intercultural, and distributed teams; (10) perform with high degree of autonomy and responsibility; (11) demonstrate entrepreneurial attitude towards Industry 4.0 related businesses and its problems; and (12) demonstrate continuous self-development by effectively improving competences for professional career.

2.2 Course Objectives Design

The objectives of the subject were backward design based on the PLOs due to considering students' viewpoints (Reynolds & Kearns, 2016). As information and communication technologies connect the world into one, today's companies are challenged by increasingly aggressive competition to satisfy dynamic customer demands. Digital transformation will be indispensable, and having an ability to mimic a physical world into a virtual world will become necessary to companies for assessing scenarios before they even occur, resulting in effective operations, better failure prevention, and attractive offerings. This course aims to build student competence in digital transformation, digital factory modeling, and digital factory analysis. The students will also practice the knowledge gained in a case study factory.

2.3 Course Learning Outcomes Design

Course Learning Outcomes (CLOs) are alignments the course objectives (Okutsu, DeLaurentis, Brophy, & Lambert, 2013). The students on the completion of this course would be able to achieve the digital factory's CLOs, as shown in Table 1.

According to a syllabus, every academic course has a syllabus, which is a subject to be studied in a particular course designed by instructors and students (Chung, Lee, & Kim, 2015). The syllabus consists of rules, responsibilities, contents, activities, assessment technique, and expectations associated with the course as well

as student's guide through the course. Moreover, the syllabus provides an extension of homework and subject oriented assignments. In this study, the course syllabus of the digital factory subject is proposed to complete its modules.

The subject is a required course of the new Master's degree program. This course describes important features of Industry 4.0 and attributes of digital technology for modelling and simulating industrial control systems. A new generation of workers is created based on the digital factory subject's syllabus. Thus, existing skills of workers are replaced by required competences of key technologies: autonomous robots, simulation, horizontal and vertical system integration, the industrial sensorization, cybersecurity, additive manufacturing, and augmented reality. The course syllabus of this course contains three modules, as shown in Table 2.

Table 1. CLOs of the digital factory subject.

CLO	Description
1	The students on the completion of this course would be able to understand the strategic differences between traditional factory and digital factory.
2	The students on the completion of this course would be able to understand the capacities and limitations of digital technologies available nowadays.
3	The students on the completion of this course would be able to formulate a data model representing data streamlining in a production line of an existing traditional factory using a data flow diagram (DFD).
4	The students on the completion of this course would be able to simulate the dynamic behavior of a production line and identify locations which must be closely monitored to keep productivity in control, as well as to prevent work defects and machine breakdowns.
5	The students on the completion of this course would be able to propose a digital factory platform of a case study factory in a virtual environment upon what have been learned.

Table 2. Details of course syllabus.

Module	Topic
Introduction to digital factory: road to digital transformation	Lean product lifecycle management towards digital factory, technologies for digital transformation, and integration of technologies for digital factory
Digital factory modeling: how to formulate a virtual world	Cyber-physical systems and data security, data flow model concept and construction, and simulation of a production line
Digital factory analysis: from analysis to factory solutions	Factory digitalization, factory critical points identification and suggestions for improvement, future trends of digital factory

2.4 Course Assessment Design

A course assessment is a significant task of course design, it is always used at the end for every course. Moreover, the course assessment, which can serve reinforced learning objectives provides feedback from students to improve tailored instruction and targeted feedback (Arts, Jaspers, & Joosten-ten Brinke, 2016). Students are motivated to pay attention in the courses by the assessment. The information can be employed to make changes during the current course. There are two existing assessment in education: formative and summative approaches. The formative approach can be defined as a variety of methods that instructors use to assess the learning outcomes and ongoing feedbacks. On the contrary, the summative approach is to assess learning experiences at the completion of a learning sequence by comparing it against CLOs (Dixson & Worrell, 2016). This approach allows the students and instructors to gather information about how well the course is meeting the needs of the students (Heitink, Van der Kleij, Veldkamp, Schildkamp, & Kippers, 2016). However, using a single approach is inadequate for the course assessment. Hence, an integrating of formative and summative approach is employed to assess the learning outcomes at the ends of each module (Buchholtz, Krosanke, Orschulik, & Vorhölter, 2018).

This section aims to measure the knowledge and learning experiences based on CLOs, which are specific and measurable statements for the completion of learning's units. CLOs are written with verb phrases to declare demonstrable actions by the achievement of learning activities (Jian, 2019; Kent, Laslo, & Rafaeli, 2016). The goal of course assessment is to evoke information about learning experiences and modify teaching approaches (Davis, 2016; Reinholz, 2015). To assess the CLOs, a rubric as a standard criterion is a scoring guide with criteria and is developed to evaluate students' learning outcomes (Stoller, 2015). There are five rubrics to assess each accomplishment of the digital factory's CLOs. Each rubric is divided into five scales reflecting the students' experiences precisely, as illustrated in Table 3. The five rating scales are commonly used to measure in various

areas because of well interpretation (Meethom & Koohathongsumrit, 2018). Where level 1 to level 5 stand for scores of 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100, respectively.

Table 3. Assessment rubric for each CLO.

CLO	Level	Description
1	1	Students can describe the strategic differences between traditional factory and digital factory in the classroom.
	2	Students can describe the strategic differences between traditional factory and digital factory either in the classroom or examination.
	3	Students can describe the difference between traditional and digital factory both in the classroom and examination.
	4	Students can describe the difference between traditional and digital factory including the examples for improving traditional factory into digital factory either in the classroom or examination.
	5	Students can describe the difference between traditional and digital factory including the examples for improving traditional factory into digital factory both in the classroom and examination.
2	1	Students can describe the capacities and limitations of digital technologies available nowadays in the classroom.
	2	Students can describe the capacities and limitations of digital technologies available nowadays either in the classroom or examination.
	3	Students can describe the capacities and limitations of digital technologies available nowadays both in the classroom and examination.
	4	Students can describe the capacities and limitations of digital technologies available nowadays including the examples for improving traditional factory into digital factory either in the classroom or examination.
	5	Students can describe the capacities and limitations of digital technologies available nowadays including the examples for improving traditional factory into digital factory both in the classroom and examination.
3	1	Students can propose the data streamlining in a production line of an existing traditional factory.
	2	Students can formulate the data model representing data streamlining in a production line of an existing traditional factory using DFD for improvement and advantage.
	3	Students can formulate the data model representing data streamlining in a production line of an existing traditional factory using DFD for improvement in investment, rate of return, feasibility, new process work, and new opportunity.
	4	The data model is accepted by a case study.
	5	The data model is installed in a case study.
4	1	Students can describe the dynamic behavior and monitoring locations of a production line.
	2	Student can describe the dynamic behavior and monitoring locations of a production line either in the classroom or examination.
	3	Students can describe the dynamic behavior and monitoring locations of a production line both in the classroom and examination.
	4	Students can describe the dynamic behavior and monitoring locations of a production line including the examples for improving traditional factory into digital factory either in the classroom or examination.
	5	Students can describe the dynamic behavior and monitoring locations of a production line including the examples for improving traditional factory into digital factory both in the classroom and examination.
5	1	Students can describe a digital factory platform of a case study factory in a virtual environment.
	2	Student can describe a digital factory platform of a case study factory in a virtual environment either in the classroom or examination.
	3	Students can describe a digital factory platform of a case study factory in a virtual environment both in the classroom and examination.
	4	Students can describe a digital factory platform of a case study factory in a virtual environment including the examples for improving traditional factory into digital factory either in the classroom or examination.
	5	Students can describe a digital factory platform of a case study factory in a virtual environment including the examples for improving traditional factory into digital factory both in the classroom and examination.

2.5 Teaching Guidelines Design

For the first module, an instructor shows videos playing on traditional factories and digital factories. Students are encouraged to express their opinions of what they just have seen. Then, the students investigate the internet to find information regarding factory digitalization, the discussion of digital technologies in factories are performed. Next, advanced technologies common digital manufacturing, especially sensorized platforms are carried out by specific diagrams. Finally, the students are assigned to construct DFD diagrams of a visited factory. These diagrams are presented at the end of this course.

For the second module, the new technologies for product development are presented. The instructor shows videos playing movies on cyber-physical systems. Afterwards, the contribution and establishment of the cyber-physical systems are discussed. Then, the DFD diagrams are constructed to promote deeper understanding the cyber-physical systems. The students are allowed to find the real cases of interested cyber security. Next, the

prevention of catastrophes regarding the cyber system's under-maintenance is proposed. The cyber security and contribution are taught (Ounsri, Tabkosai, Kengpol, & Tuammee, 2020).

The traditional production is explained to specify its weaknesses. Next, the additive manufacturing is provided. Then, the students search and present the applications of additive manufacturing, which occur in aerospace and automotive, art industry, medical and even architectural industry. The lab of such manufacturing is installed. Finally, the limitations and advantages of the technology are summarized.

The introduction of virtual reality/augmented reality is clarified. The students are able to explore and discuss the applications of such technologies. The instructor identifies the principles of virtual reality/augmented reality. Then, a brief lab demonstration on virtual reality/augmented reality is set. Finally, the learning experiences of these issues are criticized. Finally, groups of the students present its idea of a real case study.

Finally, for the third module, the concept in both information-managed and file-based environments for the development of robotic and automated production systems are lectured. Robot and workstation simulation development, from single-robot stations to complete production lines and zones are discussed including simulation software of information from sensor and mobile device to robotics and automated guided vehicle. The applications of industrial communications and sensors technology as well as mobile device are discussed. The data in smart factory are characterized by teaching. An equipment as sensor or mobile device is clarified to capture the real-time data. Then, the students are allowed to work on the case studies of how the industry employs these technologies in controlling and monitoring the process. They also present the discovered implementation of sensor and mobile device form the self-study. Next, Lab for industrial intelligent sensors are construct to gain students' learning experiences. Afterwards, the strengths and weaknesses of these technologies are demonstrated. A field trip of an automobile industry is employed to reveal the usability of sensor and mobile device.

The instructor summarizes principles of traditional manufacturing and points out a production unit, which can work autonomously using robotics and automated guided vehicle. The applications of robot and automated guided vehicle searching from the internet are shared in the class. The students obtain experiences with laboratory of such technologies. The discussion on feasibility of employment of robot and automated guided vehicle is focused. Then, the students present their project of DFD diagrams of the case study factory. Next, the project-based learning and problem-based learning are used to share ideas of "Factory of the Future" and the results are validated by the assessment rubric of CLOs. Likewise, this case-based learning on this topic is presented. Finally, instructor summarizes the course.

3 Course Implementation

This section provides an implementation of the digital factory subject at KMUTNB. The time distribution of this subject includes 4 teaching and learning methods based on LOVE dimensions: Learning (L), Observing (O), Visiting (V), and Experimenting (E) (Kengpol, Koohathongsumrit, & Meethom, 2020). In every week, students must find the DFD of case study and present the strength, weakness, opportunity, and threat. Problem-based learning by main project: student presentation twice for their projects. The self-study as an active absorption takes 4 hours. The lecture as a passive absorption takes 30 hours. The visiting factory as passive immersion takes 6 hours. Finally, the workshop and laboratory as active immersion take 45 hours. The learning environments of the digital factory subject in a classroom are showed in Figure 1.

Figure 1. learning environments of the digital factory subject in a classroom.

In this course, the pilot teaching is proceeded in the second term of 2019 between June to October. There are 12 graduated students, who register for the subject. At the end of course, instructors are allowed to evaluate the CLOs of each student by using the assessment rubrics for all CLOs. The interview, self-report test, and performance measurement are adopted to approximate levels of each CLO with respect to the students. Each CLO has different expected levels: at least 3 for the first, fourth, and fifth CLOs; and at least 4 for the second and third CLOs. The levels of CLOs are illustrated in Table 4. For example, the second student can explain the difference between traditional and digital factory both in the classroom and examination. Hence, the level of this CLO is equal to 2. According to Table 4, it shows that 37 levels are accepted while 23 levels are failed. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the levels.

Table 4. Levels for all CLOs.

Student	CLO																						
	1	2	3	4	5		1	2	3	4	5		1	2	3	4	5		1	2	3	4	5
1	4	3	2	3	3	4	3	3	2	3	5	7	5	4	5	3	4	10	2	2	4	2	3
2	1	3	4	3	4	5	2	4	2	2	4	8	5	4	3	3	4	11	4	2	4	2	4
3	4	3	2	3	5	6	4	4	5	3	4	9	4	2	3	2	5	12	1	2	4	2	4

4 Course Improvement

Curriculum improvement is the process of continuously making instruction better depending on student needs (Tam, 2014). The outputs of course improvement is to aid instructors to serve effective PLOs, CLOs, learning experiences, new knowledges, and innovations based on the teaching and learning methods combining the course syllabus (Willemse et al., 2017). Under some circumstances, new modules are added; the current modules are dropped or improved. Furthermore, the existing modules are transformed to be a different type of teaching and learning methods. Actually, the course improvement clarifies its effectiveness after implementing. It can prove that students' CLOs are either absolutely complete or definitely incomplete. The feedbacks of course implementation always used to modify the CLOs and syllabus in company with other improvements in curriculum design. Finally, the outputs of course improvement provide pilot programs or courses, and the selection of compatible and appropriate instructional materials.

After implementing the course, it finds that the time spending for teaching and learning is not enough, especially for visiting factory. Some students cannot create their imagine for the smart manufacturing in Industry 4.0. In contrast, some students, who have past experiences from their jobs or businesses can apply the knowledge in the real-life case study. For the non-experience students, the repetitive teaching and learning are performed for the incomplete sub modules or main modules. Likewise, the failed students are assigned more than an hour and a half of homework. Moreover, they are invited to watch the same clips about again to learn about digital factory instead of the visiting, in which the virtual smart factory is constructed to be a simulation related to digital manufacturing technologies. The new homework for the analysis of work stations and production lines are assigned to the students. Each student is assigned a case study representing a problem of smart factory in Industry 4.0. The course assessment is then applied for the measurement of CLOs' levels. Every student must describe the benefit for the business processes with factory life-cycle. The improved levels of each CLO are given in Table 5.

Table 5. Improved levels for all CLOs.

Student	CLO																						
	1	2	3	4	5		1	2	3	4	5		1	2	3	4	5		1	2	3	4	5
1	4	4	4	3	3	4	3	5	5	3	5	7	5	4	5	3	4	10	3	4	4	4	3
2	3	4	4	3	4	5	3	4	5	5	4	8	5	4	5	3	4	11	4	4	4	3	4
3	4	4	4	3	5	6	4	4	5	3	4	9	4	4	5	4	5	12	3	5	4	3	4

Table 5 showing the improved levels are satisfied. Therefore, it can summarize that the CLOs of students are achieve the intended learning outcomes from completing the course. At the end of course, the students, who are set up for success in Industry 4.0 acquire a better understanding of the specific knowledge and skills. After

ending the course, the results applied with the case study are continuously improved by collaborating with the case study's authorities every month.

5 Discussion and Conclusion

Many applications for smart manufacturing used in Thailand are rapidly developed and installed. The jobs in Thailand are not lacking but skills needed in jobs of the smart manufacturing for Industry 4.0 are necessary. Hence, universities must play a significant task in nurturing high-skill talent the industrial needs for sustainable economic growth. The digital factory subject is one of 16 courses created in MSIE 4.0 and is developed to serve management science applied in digital technology for design, modeling, operating the manufacturing process. Many digital technologies: the cyber physical framework, virtual reality/augmented reality, additive manufacturing, sensor and mobile device technologies, robotics/automated guided vehicle for product design, data communication, monitor process, and production control are provided in the digital factory. These technologies increasingly offer cost reduction without loss of quality. This study shows the elements of academic course design: PLOs, course objectives, CLOs, assessment methods, course syllabuses, and teaching guidelines. Moreover, the implementation of the course is also presented. The course's improvement reveals the guidelines for the enhancement of students' knowledges. The benefits of this study support instructors to reach the completion of learning outcomes. Students are able to demonstrate in terms of knowledge, skills, and values upon fulfillment of the course. It can assume that students can apply their knowledges and learning experiences for future working life and the ever-changing technological challenges. For the future study, the remaining courses are examined with a new scoring and grading assessment model. The new course is created by the proposed guideline-based the Delphi method developed by (Meethom & Koohathongsumrit, 2020)

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